

DR. AMBEDKAR'S CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN INDIA

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“Unity is meaningless without the accompaniment of women. Education is fruit-less without educated women, and Agitation is incomplete without the strength of women”.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's slogan on Unity, Education and Agitation.

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Abstract

Dr. B R Ambedkar's life was a struggle for achieving human rights. He fought for the dignity of the deprived people and was also a great thinker of woman rights. Some other intellectuals before him had worked towards women empowerment but Dr. B R Ambedkar ensured that women rights were included in the constitution of India. Dr. B R Ambedkar perceived women as the victim of the unjust and rigid social system. He attacked all major religions of India for subjugating their womenfolk. He asserted that women should be provided equal opportunities of growth. He initiated various movements for the upliftment of women. He suggested measures such as education, inter-caste marriage and inter-dine as methods of removing caste and class hierarchy. He provided various legal protections in constitution to ensure that women get their due credit in the Indian society. These constitutional securities have gone a long way in ensuring women rights in modern India. The contemporary social challenges demand an in-depth investigation of his vision, rationality of his outlook and the intrinsic humanity of his ideas for practical action.

Keywords: *Social justice, Hindu Social order, Women problems, Hindu code Bill, Equality and Indian Constitution.*

INTRODUCTION

In spite of women contribution in all spheres of life and they enjoy a unique position in every society and country of the world, but they suffer in silence and belong to a class which is in a disadvantaged position on account of several barriers and impediments. It is harsh reality that

women have been ill-treated in every society for ages and India is not an exception to this universal problem. The irony lies in the fact that in our country where women are worshipped as Shakti, the atrocities are committed against her in all sections of life. Women's empowerment in legal, social, political and economic requires to be enhanced. However, empowerment and equality are based on the gender sensitivity of society towards their problems. The intensification of women's issues and rights movement all over the world is reflected in the form of various Conventions passed by the United Nations.

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar contribution was great in the field of women's empowerment who advocated for the liberation of women and gender equality in India. If there any persons worked for women's liberation in India, they were none other than **Buddha, Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar, EV.Ramasamy Periyar and Jyotirao Phule**. Without Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar, at least whatever so changes the position of Women today in India would be only question mark. There were many leaders fought for the women's Rights in India. Most of them were failed in their action. But Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar was the only person who changed the effort via Law. Women are the victim of this evil caste system. They have been carried caste from one generation to another generation. While drafting the Constitution of India, Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar was the prime mover of the welfare of women.

Dr. B R Ambedkar's Advocacy for Women's Rights:

- **Equal participation of women:** Dr. B R Ambedkar advocated for equal participation of women in both personal and professional spheres. He was the first man to raise his voice against the unequal treatment of women in factories and other workplaces.
- **No of legislations:** Dr. B R Ambedkar drafted legislation such as the Mines Maternity Benefit Act, which demanded equal pay and equal rights for coal mine workers, ensuring that the question of maternity leave for women was brought up and they were protected under labor laws.
- **Improving working conditions:** He was instrumental in reducing working hours and improving working conditions.
- **Reproductive rights of women:** Dr. B R Ambedkar was a strong believer in the reproductive rights of women and urged them to make their own choices about conception.

Dr. B R Ambedkar's Contribution to Women's Rights:

- **Hindu Code Bill:** Dr. B R Ambedkar's most important contribution to the cause of women's rights was the Hindu Code Bill, which revolutionized property and marriage practices and established laws of maintenance for women.
- **Four acts, resulting from the Bill, were passed:**
 1. The Hindu Marriage Act, 1955, which gave women the right to divorce and maintenance;
 2. The Hindu Succession Act, 1956, which gave them the legal right to inherit property;
 3. The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, which allowed women to legally adopt a child; and
 4. The Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act, 1956, which allowed women to be the natural guardian of their children.
- **Pro-women Acts:** The influence of these reforms led to other pro-women Acts such as the Equal Remuneration Act of 1976 and the Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961, which brightened the dark roads of women's struggles.

Dr. B R Ambedkar's Vision for Women's Rights:

- **Women's right to education:** Dr. B R Ambedkar believed that education was crucial for the country's progress and regularly spoke up for women's right to education, defying the Manusmriti and the Dharmashastra.
- **Targeted hierarchical social order:** He targeted the hierarchical social order and condemned it for degrading women, and believed that endogamy was the root cause of caste consolidation.
- **Caste system and atrocities on women:** His 1917 paper, titled 'Castes in India: Their Mechanism, Genesis and Development' outlines how atrocities on women are rooted in the caste system.
- **For instance:** He denounced sati, child marriage, and the condemnation of widow remarriage, which were all meant to control women.
- **Vision of equality:** Dr. B R Ambedkar's vision of equality despite caste, gender, race, and ethnicity differences is a pioneering thought of social justice.

Conclusion:

- Dr. B R Ambedkar's contribution towards women's rights is often overlooked, and he needs to be recognized as a champion of social justice, a visionary, and a philosopher. His work to empower all sections of marginalized communities needs to be acknowledged, and his vision of equality despite caste, gender, race, and ethnicity differences is a

pioneering thought of social justice. Women's rights and their liberation are crucial for building a progressive society, and Dr. B R Ambedkar's values and vision continue to guide feminist principles in India.

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